

1 **Resilience and Reassembly: Soil Microbial Succession Under Phthalate Stress and Long-**
2 **Term Biochar Amendment**

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Abstract

20 Phthalic acid esters (PAEs), as persistent organic pollutants, alter soil microbial communities,
21 with long-term implications for ecosystem function. This study examined microbial responses
22 to PAEs contamination and the role of biochar (BC) amendment in promoting microbial
23 resilience and succession. PAEs' exposure led to modest reductions in dominant bacterial phyla
24 (Firmicutes, Proteobacteria, Actinobacteriota) and increased pollutant-degrading groups such
25 as Bdellovibrionota, Cyanobacteria, and Nitrospirota. Key nutrient-cycling phyla

26 (Acidobacteriota, Chloroflexi) declined, indicating disruption of carbon and nitrogen turnover.
27 Short-term BC application promoted plant growth-promoting and decomposer taxa (e.g.,
28 Alicyclobacillaceae, Oxalobacteraceae), suppressed opportunistic pathogens, and partially
29 restored microbial functionality through direct (sorption, habitat) and indirect (pH, enzyme
30 activity) mechanisms. Fungal communities showed higher sensitivity to both PAEs and BC.
31 While BC reduced overall fungal diversity, it increased stress-tolerant taxa such as
32 *Gibellulopsis piscis* and *Solicoccozyma*. Long-term BC amendment, especially post-
33 cultivation, triggered microbial succession favoring K-strategists, particularly Actinobacteria,
34 due to their ability to degrade biochar-derived aromatic compounds and thrive in alkaline,
35 carbon-rich soils. Though bacterial diversity recovered partially after lettuce cultivation, some
36 beneficial genera (e.g., *Massilia*, *Sphingomonas*) declined, and unclassified taxa expanded
37 significantly, reflecting lasting ecological shifts. Strong β -diversity changes suggested a
38 transition toward a more specialized and resilient microbial community. Overall, biochar
39 demonstrates strong potential as a long-term soil amendment in PAEs-contaminated
40 environments by enhancing detoxification and supporting microbial recovery. However, the
41 observed trade-offs in diversity and community composition highlight the need for careful,
42 long-term monitoring to ensure sustainable bioremediation outcomes.

43

44 **Keywords:** PAEs; phthalates; bacteria; fungi; soil microbiota; soil mycobiota

1. Introduction

45 Phthalic acid esters (PAEs), semi-volatile organic compounds, have been recognized as
46 emerging pollutants recently. The plastic film and microplastics could contain about 20–60 %
47 of PAEs (Sun et al., 2023), which are considered the markers of microplastic pollution (Chang
48 and Wang, 2023). PAEs are widely present in water, air, and soil due to their easy leaking from
49 the polymer matrix (weak hydrogen bonds and Van der Waals forces), high mobility, and low

50 biodegradability (Xiangyu Liu et al., 2024a). Up to 70 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ of PAEs may be supplied daily,
51 considering direct (dermal, respiratory, and digestive) (Net et al., 2015) and indirect human
52 exposure (Xue et al., 2020), with polluted food being a main source (Sun et al., 2023). PAEs
53 toxicity is ascribed to endocrine disruption (Miranowicz-Dzierżawska, 2023), carcinogenic and
54 mutagenic effects on humans and animals, high oxidative stress (cytotoxicity) (Chang and
55 Wang, 2023), and lower levels of photosynthetic pigments, chlorophylls, and carotenoids (Yao
56 et al., 2022) in plant cells. Therefore, the US EPA and European Union have classified six PAEs
57 (dimethyl phthalate, DMP; diethyl phthalate, DEP; dibutyl phthalate, DBP; butyl benzyl
58 phthalate, BBP; bis(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate, DEHP; and di-n-octyl phthalate, DNOP) as
59 environmental priority pollutants that have to be monitored.

60 PAEs discharged into the air, water, and wastewater end up in the soil (Li et al., 2023).
61 The concentration of di-iso-butyl phthalate (DiBP) and DBP in farmland soil reached 0.017–
62 1.63 g g^{-1} d.w. and 0.009–2.74 g g^{-1} d.w., respectively (Xue et al., 2020). The residues of
63 agricultural films, due to the application of plastic mulch in agriculture (Changcai Wu et al.,
64 2022) are connected with the transfer of PAEs within the soil and into the plants. The residual
65 film may affect soil biota by increasing the alpha diversity of bacterial communities, therefore
66 changing the bacterial community's structure and generating significant disturbances in
67 bacterial function. Increased diversity indicates that a higher number of microorganisms must
68 be involved in the PAEs mitigation in the soil (Sun et al., 2023).

69 Biochar (BC) is a carbon-rich material obtained from biomass in the absence of oxygen,
70 which has gained a lot of attention recently, mainly due to its low cost, waste management, and
71 surface properties (Wu et al., 2019). Soil amendment with biochar (1-2 wt.% being the most
72 effective and practically justified (Campos et al., 2020)) increased soil organic matter (SOM),
73 total carbon, nitrogen, and C/N ratio (Xiaoyu Wang et al., 2024). There are several
74 unquestionable advantages of BC application into the soil (Chuchu Wu et al., 2022): improved

75 soil quality (increased aggregation, pH, and cation exchange capacity (Wu et al., 2019)) and
76 productivity/fertility (source of available nutrients, adsorbent of toxic pollutants, and shelter for
77 microorganisms, decomposing toxins (Cheng et al., 2017)).

78 BC is used for the adsorption of many organic (Ahmed and Hameed, 2020) and
79 inorganic substances (Yin et al., 2020) from various matrices. The strong immobilization of
80 compounds onto the BC surface reduces their bioavailability. The application of BC for PAEs
81 immobilization (Sokołowski et al., 2024b) and degradation (Guan et al., 2023) was also applied
82 to lower their environmental hazard. The application of BC into PAEs contaminated soil may
83 solve two main problems: i) immobilization of pollutants through adsorption, and ii) nutrient
84 supplementation for soil organisms participating in the PAEs decomposition (Saxena et al.,
85 2013). It was observed that when wheat straw-derived BC was added to the soil, a very strong
86 interaction between DMP and the formed BC-soil complexes was noted (Yan and Quan, 2020).
87 For the sorption mechanism, both chemisorption (π - π electron donor-acceptor interaction) and
88 physisorption (pore-filling and hydrophobic interactions) were responsible. Such interaction
89 resulted from introducing BC rich in the surface functional groups that interact with soil
90 minerals. However, in the soil, BC undergoes several biotic and abiotic processes leading to its
91 aging e.g. lowered C content (but increased soil water-soluble organic matter levels different
92 than feedstock- and pyrolysis-derived), increased surface area, and increased content of surface
93 O-containing functional groups (carboxylic and phenolic), affecting BC interaction with soil
94 constituents (including toxins) (Yan and Quan, 2020). BC is a source of persistent free radicals,
95 activating Reactive Oxygen Species (ROS) and electron transfer between BC and microbial
96 cells (direct interspecific electron transfer between microbial cells) and between soil and
97 microbial cells (the direct extracellular electron transfer) (Zhu et al., 2017).

98 A critical consideration is the physicochemical characteristics of biochar, as these can
99 exert adverse effects on soil ecosystems (Brtnicky et al., 2021). In terms of nutrient balance,

100 excessive biochar application may reduce fungal abundance and shift microbial communities
101 toward bacterial dominance. The disadvantages of BC, such as the presence of toxic
102 components like polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs), and heavy metals, may also be
103 observed (Hilber et al., 2012). The properties of biochar, including its environmental safety,
104 can be regulated by tuning the feedstock and pyrolysis parameters.

105 In the sorption of PAEs, two main BC properties are crucial: O-functional groups (-
106 COOH and -OH), which increase the BC hydrophilicity, lowering the adsorption of
107 hydrophobic PAEs, and porosity, which increases the overall adsorption (Yan and Quan, 2020).
108 Additionally, in the soil, the dissolved organic matter (DOM) may increase the adsorption of
109 PAEs onto BC-soil composites (Yan and Quan, 2020). With proceeding aging, the interaction
110 of BC and PAEs may be lowered, leading to their desorption (as noted for DMP (Yan and Quan,
111 2020)) and transport with water. In our previous study, such behavior, which increased PAEs'
112 bioavailability and toxicity, was observed during the post-cultivation of vegetables in PAEs-
113 contaminated soil (Sokołowski et al., 2024b).

114 The previous studies indicate that PAEs' presence in the soil affects the soil
115 microorganisms' community composition (Changcai Wu et al., 2022), affecting soil enzymatic
116 activity. Similarly, a few studies described the bacterial community in BC-amended soil (Zhu
117 et al., 2019). Several studies show that the BC amendment enhances the microbial biomass and
118 microbial activity in soils contaminated with PAHs (Liu et al., 2015; Zhao et al., 2022),
119 petroleum hydrocarbons (H. Wang et al., 2024), and polychlorinated biphenyls (Hoang et al.,
120 2021). However, there is a lack of information on the fate of the soil bacteria and fungi in PAEs-
121 polluted soil under the BC amendment over a prolonged time. To address these points, the
122 objectives of the presented paper were i) estimation of the effect of BC amendment of PAEs
123 polluted soil on soil microbiota, and ii) determination of how soil community structure reacts
124 over prolonged time under cultivation of the vegetables. The soil was artificially contaminated

125 with six priority PAEs (DMP, DEP, DBP, BBP, DNOP, and DEHP), and 16S rRNA and ITS2
126 sequencing were performed to study the effect of BC addition on PAEs immobilization and soil
127 microbiome.

128 2. Methods

129 2.1. Experimental design

130 A standard mixture of $1 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ in hexane of 6 priority PAEs was prepared from
131 individual stock standard solutions (DMP, DEP, DBP, BBP, DEHP, DnOP, Sigma Aldrich,
132 Poland). Biochar obtained from sunflowers (*Helianthus L.*) (labeled as BC-Sf) was pyrolyzed
133 at 600°C in a nitrogen atmosphere for 3 hours. It was tested for its physicochemical properties
134 described in the previous paper (Sokołowski et al., 2024c). Among the produced BC, BC-Sf
135 was characterized by the lowest ash content (6.7%), hydrophilicity (O/C ratio= 0.046), and
136 polarity ((N+O)/C=0.057), whereas the C content (86.67%) and total organic carbon content
137 (TOC 878.52 mg g^{-1}) were the highest. BC-Sf was chosen for this study as the material that
138 reduced PAEs' bioavailability to lettuce most effectively. Additionally, this material was
139 characterized by very low content of bioavailable fraction of PAHs (0.124 ng/L) and did not
140 show any toxicity towards bacteria in the Microtox® test (Sokołowski et al., 2024a).

141 The topsoil samples (0-20 cm) of the agricultural soil from Podborcze, Poland
142 ($50^\circ41'47.5''\text{N } 22^\circ50'41.3''\text{E}$) were air-dried, sieved (0.25 mm), homogenized, and divided into
143 several groups (340 g each). The agricultural acidic brown soil developed from deep loess was
144 characterized by $\text{pH}_{\text{KCl}} = 5.3\text{-}6.2$, organic carbon content of 2.986 g kg^{-1} (and TOC of 33.33 mg
145 L^{-1}), medium available P content (59.3 mg g^{-1}), whereas other nutrient content was high (Mg
146 73 mg kg^{-1}) or very high (K 346.9 mg kg^{-1}). The control (uncultivated soil) (labeled as S), soil
147 spiked with 1 mL of PAEs mixture containing $1 \mu\text{g/mL}$ of each tested compound (labeled as S-
148 PAEs), soil spiked with 1 mL of PAEs mixture containing $1 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ of each tested compound
149 and 1 wt.% addition of BC-Sf before (labeled as S-PAEs-BC-Sf) and after lettuce (*Lactuca*

150 *sativa L.*) cultivation (labeled as S-PAEs-BC-Sf-L) were compared. 1% wt. BC addition was
151 performed, being economically and practically reasonable (Guan et al., 2023). Experiments
152 were performed in triplicate. The pot experiment was conducted for 6 weeks, and the detailed
153 procedure was described in (Sokołowski et al., 2024c).

154 **2.2. DNA isolation**

155 Isolation of the microbial DNA was conducted with the DNeasy PowerSoil Pro Kit
156 (Qiagen, Hilden, Germany). First, 500 mg of the soil sample was homogenized with the
157 FastPrep instrument (MP Biomedicals, Solon, OH, USA) at 4 m s^{-1} for 20 seconds, and then,
158 the isolation of the DNA was continued with the QIAQUBE robot (Qiagen, Hilden, Germany)
159 according to the manufacturer's protocol. The samples were eluted in 50 μl of the Eluent and
160 stored at -20°C until the preparation of the libraries.

161 **2.3. Amplicon sequencing and bioinformatic analysis**

162 The amplicon sequencing and bioinformatical processing of the data of 16Sv4 and ITS2
163 regions were performed on the Illumina MiSeq instrument, as described before (Siegieda et al.,
164 2024). Importing the amplicone sequence variants (ASV) table, taxonomy table, and metadata
165 into RStudio (v. 2023.12.1 Build 402, Posit Software, PBC, R v. 4.1.2) and creating separate
166 phyloseq objects for 16S and ITS amplicon data resulted in 187,131 and 152,261 reads,
167 respectively. Then, repeated rarefaction at 5,900 and 4,900 was conducted with the Mirlyn
168 package (Cameron et al., 2021). Alpha diversity was expressed as the Effective Number of
169 Species (ENS) (Jost, 2006) after calculating the exponential of the Shannon entropy index.
170 Next, for the β -diversity of bacteria and fungi, Principal Coordinates Analysis (PCoA) was
171 conducted using a matrix based on the weighted UniFrac or Bray-Curtis algorithm,
172 respectively. To evaluate β -diversity differences across groups, a permutational multivariate
173 analysis of variance (PERMANOVA) and beta dispersion with 9999 permutations were used.

174 Taxa bar plots representing the 15 most abundant taxa for phylum and species were presented
175 in Figures 1 and 2.

176 3. Results and discussion

177 3.1. The effect of PAEs on soil bacteria

178 The study was divided into three stages: (i) assessing the impact of PAEs on soil
179 microbiota, (ii) evaluating the effect of BC amendment on the microbiome of PAEs-
180 contaminated soil, and (iii) examining microbial changes after prolonged BC-soil contact
181 following lettuce cultivation in PAEs-polluted, BC-amended soil. Biochar addition was found
182 to reshape the soil microbial structure, primarily altering community composition without
183 significantly changing total microbial biomass or overall metabolic activity (Zhu et al., 2019).

a)

b)

184 Figure 1. Relative abundance of bacteria in tested conditions at a) phylum, b) species level.

185

186 In uncontaminated soil (Figure 1a), *Firmicutes*, *Proteobacteria*, and *Actinobacteriota*
 187 dominated the microbial community, comprising approximately 65–70% of the total bacterial
 188 population. At the species level (Figure 1b), *Firmicutes* (21%) were mainly represented by
 189 *Bacillus sp.* (20%) and *Tumebacillus sp.* (~1%), *Proteobacteria* (~9%) by *Sphingomonas sp.*
 190 (5%), *Massilia sp.*, *Microvirga sp.*, and *Actinobacteriota* (7%) by *Nocardioides sp.* and
 191 unclassified *Micrococcaceae*.

192 Contamination with six priority PAEs slightly reduced the collective abundance of
193 *Firmicutes*, *Proteobacteria*, and *Actinobacteriota* (by ~2%), while increasing *Firmicutes*
194 (~4%), emphasizing their role in PAEs degradation (Xiangyu Liu et al., 2024b). PAEs promoted
195 the growth of several phyla, notably *Bdellovibrionota* (220% increase), *Cyanobacteria* (270%
196 increase), and *Nitrospirota* (350% increase), all associated with nutrient cycling and pollutant
197 degradation. Conversely, a 9–28% reduction in the abundance of phyla like *Proteobacteria*,
198 *Actinobacteriota*, *Acidobacteriota*, *Chloroflexi*, and *Planctomycetota*, crucial for organic
199 matter degradation and nutrient cycling, biofilm aggregation and other environmental processes
200 was observed (Bovio-Winkler et al., 2023; Gonçalves et al., 2024a). The decline of
201 *Acidobacteriota* and *Chloroflexi* is indicative of a possible disturbance in microbial functions
202 related to C/N cycling, but further studies (including enzyme activity assays and nutrient
203 mineralization experiments) are needed to establish a direct causal relationship. The
204 introduction of PAEs induced changes in the bacterial community, which must work more on
205 nutrient utilization.

206 *Bacillaceae* was the dominant bacterial family (>20%) under all conditions, with the
207 highest presence (~25%) in PAEs-contaminated soils and the lowest (~21%) post-lettuce
208 cultivation. *Bacillaceae* can degrade lignocellulose (Jiang et al., 2019) and participate in PAEs
209 decomposition (Xiangyu Liu et al., 2024a). PAEs presence induced the ~20 % growth of plant-
210 derived organic matter decomposers in rhizosphere from families *Chthoniobacteraceae*,
211 *Chitinophagaceae* (bacteria which was noted in biofilm formed on bio-based plastics (Nguyen
212 et al., 2023)), *Alicyclobacillaceae* (bacteria able to degrade PAHs (Chen et al., 2023), and
213 *Sphingobacteriaceae* (degrading aliphatic C to stable aromatic C (Jiang et al., 2019)), ~50 %
214 increase of *Pedospaeraceae* (plant growth promoting rhizobacteria (Brito et al., 2025), also
215 found in biofilm formed on bio-plastics (Nguyen et al., 2023)), and ~80 % of *Oxalobacteraceae*
216 (bacteria able to degrade PAHs (Chen et al., 2024) but also bio-based plastic (Nguyen et al.,

217 2023)). Significantly reduced abundance was noted for Sphingomonadaceae (organics such as
218 triclosan-degrading bacteria (Dai et al., 2022), Xanthobacteraceae (~30 %) (biomarker of
219 organic contaminants presence in the soil, such as PAHs but also As (Zhou et al., 2024)),
220 Hymenobacteraceae (stress-tolerant bacteria (Li et al., 2022)), and Unclassified Chloroflexi
221 (~40 %) (lignin and cellulose decomposing bacteria (participating in carbon and nutrient
222 cycling) (Song et al., 2024). PAEs significantly increased the complexity of the bacterial
223 community and reduced the tightness of bacterial community connections (Changcai Wu et al.,
224 2022).

225 At the species level, PAEs increased *Firmicutes*, especially *Bacillus sp.*, while reducing
226 *Proteobacteria* and *Actinobacteriota*. Endophytic bacteria like *Bacillus sp.* and *Sphingomonas*
227 *sp.*, capable of PAEs degradation, interact with root exudates and colonize plant roots (Xiangyu
228 Liu et al., 2024a). The presence of PAEs disrupted nutrient cycles (especially C and N), further
229 emphasizing the need for remediation. Although six priority PAEs were tested, they produced
230 similar impacts on microbial diversity (Changcai Wu et al., 2022). Microbial degradation of
231 PAEs involves ester bond hydrolysis, producing phthalic acid and corresponding alcohols.
232 These hydrophobic compounds disrupt bacterial membranes, especially in Gram-negative
233 species, even among PAEs-degraders (Qiao et al., 2024). PAEs' presence in the soil affected
234 the metabolism of microorganisms. In the studies 30 it was observed that some *Proteobacteria*,
235 *Actinobacteria*, *Bacteroides*, and *Firmicutes* are biomarkers of PAEs contamination (among
236 which 23 were for DMP, 12 – DBP, and 20 for DEHP) and the presence of PAEs up-regulated
237 and down-regulated of the expression of multiple metabolites with DEHP as the molecule able
238 to change the content of 50 types of metabolites (carbohydrates, lipids, amino acids, steroid
239 hormone biosynthesis, xenobiotics degradation) compared with the control including some
240 special rhizosphere signal materials, such as 4', 5-dihydroxy-7-methoxyisoflavone. On the other
241 side, it was noted that the addition of DBP promoted the biodegradation and metabolism of

242 plasticizers, including benzoate and bisphenol, stressing the role of soil microorganisms in the
243 decomposition of PAEs and microplastics (Changcai Wu et al., 2022). While functional
244 inference and taxonomic enrichment patterns suggest BC promoted the proliferation of putative
245 PAEs-degrading communities, we acknowledge that our current data do not pinpoint specific
246 catabolic genes. Future metagenomic analysis will be necessary to link BC amendments with
247 PAEs degradation pathways directly.

248

a)

b)

249 Figure 2. Relative abundance of fungi in tested conditions at a) phylum, b) species level.

250 Fungi predominated in macroaggregates rich in organic matter (Zhu et al., 2017). In
 251 PAEs-contaminated soils, fungal communities were dominated by *Ascomycota* (55%),
 252 *Basidiomycota* (13%), and *Mortierellomycota* (18%) (Figure 2a), typical fungi phyla noted in
 253 the soil (Xiaojun Liu et al., 2024). Less abundant phyla ($\leq 5\%$) included ecologically significant
 254 groups like early diverging fungi *Chytridiomycota*, able to penetrate resistant structures,
 255 releasing recalcitrant carbon (Lopez-Moya et al., 2023), *Mucoromycota*, mutualistic symbionts
 256 with most land plants, participating in the inorganic nutrients transport from the soil to the plant
 257 (Bonfante and Venice, 2020), pathogenic *Rozellomycota*, observed at high soluble N
 258 concentration (Martín-Pinto et al., 2021), cellulose and chitin degrading, and nutrients
 259 providing (Peng et al., 2024) *Olpidiomycota*, saprotrophs, and obligate parasites of both plants
 260 and animals (Taylor et al., 2015) *Blastocladiomycota*, arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi (Rivera-
 261 Becerril et al., 2017) *Glomeromycota*, putatively obligate intracellular parasites (Marino et al.,

262 2022) *Aphelidiomycota*, *Kickxellomycota*, which can survive in a dry environment (Xinxin
263 Wang et al., 2024), *Basidiobolomycota*, *Monoblepharomycota*, and unclassified fungi with
264 incertae sedis. At the species level (Figure 2b), *Ascomycota* (18%) was mainly represented by
265 unclassified *Nectriaceae* and *Solicoccozyma*. *Mortierellomycota* included *Mortierella* (7.3%)
266 and unclassified *Mortierellaceae* (9%). PAEs altered fungal nutrient utilization, as evidenced
267 by increased *Ascomycota* and *Basidiomycota*, suggesting adaptation to recalcitrant carbon.
268 Under anoxic conditions, *Mortierellomycota* was a key contributor to organic carbon
269 mineralization (Xiaojun Liu et al., 2024).

270 **3.2. Effect of Biochar Amendment on PAEs-Contaminated Soil**

271 Biochar addition enhanced the relative abundance of *Firmicutes*, *Acidobacteriota*,
272 *Verrucomicrobiota*, *Chloroflexi*, *Myxococcota*, *Gemmatimonadota*, and *Cyanobacteria*,
273 particularly *Nitrospirota*, which increased 6.5-fold, highlighting the restoration of microbial
274 functionality and nutrient availability. Conversely, *Bacteroidota*, *Patescibacteria*, and
275 *Bdellovibrionota* were suppressed, indicating BC's detoxifying role (Dai et al., 2024; Mujakić
276 et al., 2022; Nawaz et al., 2024). *Actinobacteria*, *Proteobacteria*, and *Acidobacteria* were
277 predominant bacterial phyla in the soil amended by the rice-straw-derived BC (Zhu et al., 2019).
278 The reduced abundance of *Bacteroidota* (soil quality indicators (Kruczyńska et al., 2023)),
279 *Patescibacteria* (nitrifying bacteria (Xiao et al., 2022) and predators (Li et al., 2021))
280 *Bdellovibrionota* stress the role of BC as an additive crucial in decontamination of polluted soil
281 and nutrient supplier.

282 BC increased the abundance of *Alicyclobacillaceae* (26%), *Chitinophagaceae* (36%),
283 and *Oxalobacteraceae* (~80%), while reducing lignocellulolytic *Paenibacillaceae*. Post-
284 cultivation, dominant families shifted to *Xanthobacteraceae*, *Chloroflexi*,
285 *Chthoniobacteraceae*, and *Planococcaceae*. BC also modulated species-level abundance.
286 Populations of *Thermomicrobiales*, *Bryobacter*, *Pedobacter*, *Myxococcaceae*, *Massilia*, and

287 *Tumebacillus* increased, while *Sphingomonas*, *Chloroflexi*, *Solirubrobacterales*, and
288 *Pontibacter* declined. Notably, *Sphingomonas*, *Microvirga*, and *Micrococcaceae* recovered to
289 pre-contamination levels following BC application. *Pontibacter*, a plant-growth-promoting
290 genus known for organophosphate degradation, declined from 3% to <1%. *Bacillus* spp. (22%)
291 remained dominant. These species, along with *Sphingomonas*, *Nocardioideae*, and
292 *Micrococcaceae*, play key roles in the degradation of various organic pollutants (Ali et al.,
293 2023; Guo et al., 2024), *Bryobacter* spp. increased by 66%, further indicating BC's promotion
294 of rhizobacteria and microbial stability (Pan et al., 2024). BC mechanisms include direct effects
295 (as a microbial habitat, nutrient source, and pollutant sorbent) and indirect effects (modifying
296 soil physicochemical properties, enzyme activities, microbial communication, and toxicant
297 sequestration) (Zhu et al., 2017). BC stabilizing effect on soil pH results from the presence of
298 alkaline functional groups, including lactone group, –OH, –COO–, and promoted at alkaline
299 pH, alkaline phosphatase activity suppresses the reduction of PA (Guan et al., 2023).

300 Fungal diversity also responded to BC. While phyla such as *Mortierellomycota*,
301 *Mucoromycota*, and *Rozellomycota* declined, unclassified fungi tripled in relative abundance,
302 indicating BC's biodiversity-enhancing potential. *Ascomycota* (Manici et al., 2024) increased
303 to 40%, with a marked rise in *Gibellulopsis piscis* (388% increase) (Zare et al., 2007) and
304 *Nectriaceae* (285% increase) (Rissi et al., 2024) belong to saprobes; therefore, the increase in
305 the content of SOM as a result of adding BC to the soil stimulates the growth of these species.
306 These pathogenic fungi were recognized as being connected the most among microbes
307 colonizing wheat straw residues during decomposition with climate change (global warming)
308 (Fareed et al., 2021). The highest increase in the abundance of other pathogens, like weak
309 pathogens of plants (Alisaac and Götz, 2022) *Gibellulopsis nigrescens* (11 times),
310 entomopathogenic (Moharram et al., 2021) *Botryotrichum atrogriseum* (~6 times), and invasive
311 *Acremonium* sp. (~ 5 times) stress that although the BC induces the growth of pollutants-

312 degrading bacteria, it may favor the growth of pathogenic fungi. The relative abundance of
313 Basidiomycota increased approximately threefold, driven primarily by unclassified
314 *Solicoccozyma* (rising from 3% in PAE-polluted soil to 8% in the S + PAEs + BC treatment).
315 In contrast, the reduced abundance of Mortierellomycota (9% of total fungal sequences) was
316 associated with decreased accumulation of active carbon and particulate organic carbon,
317 particularly within the heavy-fraction pool, resulting in lower availability of soil organic carbon
318 for fungal utilization. Notably, the analysis also detected *Talaromyces atroroseus* (2.4% of total
319 fungal taxa), a species known for the production of red pigments.

320 Biochar undergoes aging in soil due to various environmental factors, including exposure
321 to light, humidity, and microbial activity. This aging process alters its physicochemical
322 characteristics, such as increasing the proportion of oxygen-containing functional groups,
323 enhancing surface polarity and hydrophilicity, and modifying porosity (Krzyszczak-Turczyn et
324 al., 2024). Consequently, evaluating the long-term impacts of BC amendment requires
325 consideration beyond its initial application (Zhu et al., 2019).

326 Following lettuce cultivation in PAEs-contaminated soil, a modest increase was
327 observed in the relative abundance of the three dominant bacterial phyla involved in carbon
328 cycling and plant growth promotion (such as Firmicutes, Proteobacteria, and Actinobacteriota),
329 rising from 65% to 70%. Notably, Actinobacteriota abundance exhibited a significant increase,
330 from approximately 12% to 20%. Additional increases were recorded in Acidobacteriota
331 (~30%) and Chloroflexi (~50%). Acidobacteriota contribute to the degradation of plant-derived
332 polymers and are key players in C, N, S, and trace metal cycling (Gonçalves et al., 2024b),
333 while Actinobacteriota are critical for the structural complexity and resilience of the soil
334 microbial community, particularly under conditions of fluctuating moisture and pH (Pan et al.,
335 2024).

336 Previous studies demonstrated that lettuce roots in PAEs-contaminated soils were more
337 branched, shorter, and denser with numerous root hairs, indicative of water stress induced by
338 PAEs toxicity (Sokołowski et al., 2024c). A notable increase (230%) in the proportion of
339 unclassified bacterial taxa was also observed, suggesting a pronounced shift in the microbial
340 community structure under combined PAEs and BC influence. The phylum Nitrospirota
341 exhibited the most substantial relative increase. Specific bacterial families showed distinct
342 responses. The relative abundances of Chthoniobacteraceae and Planococcaceae, both involved
343 in hydrolysis and fermentation during anaerobic digestion (Krushna Bhujbal et al., 2025),
344 increased by 74% and 43%, respectively. The relative abundance of Xanthobacteraceae and
345 unclassified Chloroflexi increased by 2.7-fold and 3.2-fold, respectively. In contrast, the
346 abundances of Chitinophagaceae (88% decrease), Sphingobacteriaceae (89% decrease),
347 Oxalobacteraceae (99% decrease), and Hymenobacteraceae (~100% decrease) were markedly
348 reduced compared to the control.

349 In control soils, genera such as *Bacillus*, *Sphingomonas*, *Nocardioides*, *Pontibacter*, and
350 unclassified Micrococcaceae comprised approximately 33% of the total bacterial community.
351 In post-cultivation, this share decreased to ~21%. Significant reductions were observed for
352 *Pontibacter* (99% decrease), *Massilia* (98% decrease), notable for biopolymer degradation and
353 phosphate solubilization (Chhetri et al., 2024), *Pedobacter* (78% decrease), unclassified
354 *Myxococcaceae* (78% decrease), *Sphingomonas* (75% decrease), *Nocardioides* (75% decrease),
355 *Microvirga* (65% decrease), capable of degrading flonicamid insecticide (Zheng et al., 2024),
356 and unclassified Micrococcaceae (48 %).

357 Our findings, in contrast, underscore the critical role of PAEs in modulating microbial
358 dynamics effects that are strongly dependent on PAEs type, concentration, and inherent soil
359 properties. Humic substances may stabilize PAEs, extending their persistence but also
360 supporting aerobic bacterial growth that facilitates their eventual degradation. The proliferation

361 of PAHs-degrading bacteria (e.g., various Actinobacteria and *Nocardioidea*) suggests that
362 PAHs present in BC did not exert toxic effects at the concentrations applied, and may have been
363 gradually degraded over time. Actinobacteria, known colonizers of BC-rich and alkaline
364 environments, may exert competitive advantages by secreting antimicrobial metabolites or by
365 utilizing phenolic compounds derived from BC's aromatic carbon structures, enhancing the
366 broader microbial capacity for phenol degradation. The temporal shift in dominance from
367 Proteobacteria to Actinobacteria likely reflects a microbial succession from r-strategists
368 (rapidly metabolizing labile carbon fractions) to K-strategists (adapting to more recalcitrant
369 substrates) (Zheng et al., 2024). While Gammaproteobacteria are identified as key
370 chemolithoautotrophic CO₂ fixers during short-term BC incubation (Zhu et al., 2019), their role
371 diminished over time, as evidenced by a sharp decline in *Massilia* abundance post-cultivation.

372 In the fungal community, long-term BC amendment and lettuce cultivation led to a two-
373 fold increase in Olpidiomyota, a phylum considered an indicator of microbial succession (Li
374 et al., 2019), as well as increases in Aphelidiomyota, Basidiomycota, and a near four-fold rise
375 in unclassified fungi, indicating a stimulation of fungal proliferation. The relative abundance of
376 Mortierellomycota decreased further to 7%, while Ascomycota remained stable (~40%). Within
377 Ascomycota, several taxa showed marked increases: *Gibellulopsis nigrescens* (10-fold),
378 *Botryotrichum atrogriseum* (7-fold), *Acremonium* spp. (6-fold), *Gibellulopsis piscis* (4-fold),
379 *Trichocladium* spp. (3-fold), and unclassified *Nectriaceae* (2-fold). The most substantial
380 increase (25-fold) was observed in unclassified *Hypocreales incertae sedis*, a group often
381 associated with drought-stressed plants and soils with disrupted microbiomes (Yang et al.,
382 2020).

383

a)

b)

c)

d)

384 Figure 3. a) α diversity, b) β diversity of the bacterial community, c) α fungal diversity, d) β
 385 diversity of the fungal community.

386 Microbial diversity was assessed using two alpha diversity indices, Shannon and
 387 Simpson (ENS), to evaluate the impacts of PAEs contamination, BC amendment, and lettuce
 388 cultivation (Table 1). Differences in community composition were further explored using
 389 Principal Coordinate Analysis (PCoA) (Figure 3), which revealed that both PAEs
 390 contamination and BC amendment significantly influenced the bacterial community structure.

391 **Table 1.** Alpha diversity indices of bacterial and fungal communities under various
 392 treatments (mean \pm SE, n = 3).

index	Shannon	Simpson	ENS
S	6.268 \pm 0.473	0.997 \pm 0.001	584.5638 \pm 293.4069
S+PAEs	5.627 \pm 0.321	0.995 \pm 0.0003	292.0446 \pm 108.3463
S+PAEs+BC-Sf	5.655 \pm 0.105	0.995 \pm 0.001	287.2897 \pm 40.6001
S+PAEs+BC-Sf+L	6.230 \pm 0.567	0.997 \pm 0.002	595.9871 \pm 330.030
S+PAEs	4.645 \pm 0.163	0.981 \pm 0.002	105.4699 \pm 17.0308
S+PAEs+BC-Sf	4.090 \pm 0.498	0.964 \pm 0.011	65.5804 \pm 32.7234
S+PAEs+BC-Sf+L	3.783 \pm 0.002	0.958 \pm 0.001	44.1786 \pm 5.4804

393
 394 Higher Simpson index values indicate a community dominated by rare taxa. The
 395 observed decreases in the Simpson and Shannon indices following PAEs contamination and
 396 BC amendment suggest an initial reduction in diversity. However, these indices returned to
 397 near-control levels after lettuce cultivation, indicating partial recovery of the microbial
 398 community. Thus, the BC application had a transient effect on bacterial α -diversity, with limited
 399 long-term impact on β -diversity. In contrast, fungal communities displayed significant changes
 400 in both α - and β -diversity following BC application, underscoring their crucial role in the
 401 bioremediation of PAEs-contaminated soils.

402 The application of biochar can significantly affect the soil microbial communities
 403 involved in PAEs biodegradation. BC, providing porous microhabitats, adsorptive surfaces, and
 404 a stable carbon source, can suppress the survival and activity of PAEs-degrading
 405 microorganisms (such as *Pseudomonas*, *Sphingomonas*, and *Bacillus* spp. (Lu et al., 2019;
 406 Zhang et al., 2020). The result of BC aging is an enhanced abundance of oxygen-containing
 407 functional groups (e.g., hydroxyl, carbonyl, and carboxyl) (Krzyszczak-Turczyn et al., 2024),

408 which can modify interactions with PAEs, their adsorption and bioavailability, and promote co-
409 metabolic degradation pathways (Zuo et al., 2024). However, very strong sorption of PAEs by
410 BC may limit their accessibility to microorganisms, reducing degradation rates. These
411 outcomes are influenced by the biochar feedstock and its resulting physicochemical properties,
412 as well as pyrolysis temperature and application rate, underscoring the importance of selecting
413 tailored biochar formulations to sustain bacterial-mediated biodegradation of PAEs. In contrast,
414 a recent meta-analysis by Deshoux et al. (Deshoux et al., 2023) demonstrated that fungal
415 diversity indices were primarily governed by soil characteristics, being highest in medium-
416 textured soils with low pH but elevated soil organic carbon content.

417 Biochar amendment promoted the expression of genes involved in secondary metabolite
418 biosynthesis and degradation, including metabolic, transcriptional, and translational pathways
419 relevant to the biodegradation of PAEs and BC-associated PAHs. The inclusion of pH-
420 modifying agents helped maintain pH stability and enhance the availability of organic carbon,
421 thereby restructuring the microbial community towards dominance by Actinobacteria and
422 Proteobacteria, and stimulating beneficial fungal taxa within Ascomycota (Zhu et al., 2019).

423 **Conclusions**

424 Environmental factors, including fluctuations in temperature and variations in soil
425 moisture, play a critical role in determining the aging dynamics of biochar in soil systems.
426 Changes in temperature can accelerate oxidative and microbial processes, thereby altering the
427 surface chemistry, porosity, and functional group composition of BC. Similarly, variations in
428 soil moisture influence oxygen availability, redox potential, and microbial activity, which
429 collectively affect the rate and pathways of BC transformation. These processes not only modify
430 the physicochemical stability of BC but also shape its interactions with soil organic matter,
431 nutrients, and first of all, pollutants. Furthermore, the development and activity of soil microbial
432 communities are directly linked to these environmental drivers, as shifts in microbial

433 composition and function can enhance or inhibit BC degradation. Ultimately, such
434 environmental influences govern the long-term persistence of BC in soils and its role in
435 regulating nutrient cycling, contaminant immobilization, and plant - soil interactions. PAEs
436 contamination moderately reduced dominant bacterial phyla (e.g., Firmicutes, Proteobacteria)
437 while boosting pollutant-degrading groups such as Bdellovibrionota and Nitrospirota. This shift
438 disrupted nutrient cycling by suppressing key decomposers like Acidobacteriota and
439 Chloroflexi. Beneficial PAEs-degrading species (e.g., *Bacillus*, *Sphingomonas*) increased,
440 indicating microbial adaptation. BC application rapidly altered microbial communities,
441 enhancing plant growth-promoting and decomposer taxa while reducing opportunistic
442 pathogens through both direct (habitat provision) and indirect (pH, enzyme activity)
443 mechanisms. Fungal communities were more sensitive; BC reduced overall fungal diversity but
444 favored stress-tolerant taxa. Long-term BC use led to microbial succession marked by a rise in
445 Actinobacteria and unclassified taxa, indicating adaptation to carbon-rich, alkaline
446 environments. After lettuce cultivation, bacterial diversity partially recovered, though some
447 beneficial genera declined. BC enhanced degradation-related gene expression and improved
448 soil conditions, supporting microbial function. Overall, BC offers promise for remediating
449 PAEs-contaminated soils, though long-term impacts on microbial diversity warrant close
450 evaluation.

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